

Gregory of Nyssa's oration 40

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This oration was written and preached for the catechumens who used to postpone their baptismal practice, at risk of losing their salvation, heaven, and a life free from sin, according to Gregory of Nyssa. This oration is part of a larger body of catechetical works, that try to proselytize new Christians and preach the word of Jesus Christ. It is common in the fourth century to meet orations like Gregory's; the early church did not have the political and social power it wished for and, therefore, it managed to find ways to make its presence bolder and stronger. Thus, orations like this one, would contribute to a better understanding of Christianity as well as to proselytize new members of the Christian community effortlessly. The holy baptism of the catechumens is indicated picturesquely in Gregory of Nyssa's orations. Gregory of Nyssa indicates baptism as a medicine: a medicine that cures all the sins of the body and the soul. Water is a healing material and a process of the body's cure and rebirth. Water was always necessary for the baptismal practice, as it is been holy since Jesus' baptism. It is an integral part of baptism to pray. Praying was an act of salvation and dialogue with God. The baptism prayer is placed with the baptism, for the baptismist, the baptized, and the people around. The word "Baptist" brings our attention to this point. Were there still Baptists in the fourth century? Or Gregory implicates the work of the priest as a Baptist? That remains unknown in this oration. There is a phenomenon in late antiquity of the laic baptizing catechumens, mostly in emergencies (e.g., in the case of a lethal disease). However, Gregory of Nyssa does not elaborate on these roles exactly in his oration on baptism. What we do see in Gregory's work is an appeal for baptism in case of sudden death, which leads us to examine life expectancy in late antiquity, as we will see later. Gregory's oration addresses those who delay baptism. We can conclude the fact that the catechumens were not convinced easily to be baptized, especially when they were healthy. Gregory refers to them as "slaves of the sin". Using the example of a catechumen who baptized himself with all the waters of nature right before his violent death, he illustrates the importance of baptism with all the waters of nature. This example confirms the fact that the emotion that led the catechumens into baptism is fear, just as when the plague hit in Justinian's time when people sought help and the blessing of baptism. In addition, Gregory mentions that baptism was the first option the catechumens used during natural disasters and invasions. Therefore, we conclude that baptism was not a popular option for the newly catechumens. Gregory of Nyssa implies that many people remained in the catechetical phase for quite a long. "How long will you be a student learning the alphabet", he wonders. He emphatically mentions in his oration the possibility of young people dying from a disease, an accident or choking, or a heart attack. Through this way, he persuades the catechumens to seek the baptism in order to protect their bodies and soul and let the Lord prevail over them. For an older catechumen, it is easier to be baptized as they are approaching the end of their life. It wasn't just Gregory of Nyssa who tried to get catechumens baptized. During the fourth and fifth centuries, we see other church fathers, like John Chrysostom, trying to convince the catechumens (and not just them) to insert baptism into their lives. Similarly to Gregory of Nyssa, John Chrysostom dedicated whole orations on holy baptism in order to get baptism to prevail over the catechumens' lives. Gregory of Nyssa's oration has multiple levels: the catechetical level, baptismal practices, baptismal roles, emotional history, the aging process, and death cases. Gregory knitted the baptismal scarf step by step, in order to persuade the catechumens to get baptized immediately. Through different emotions and examples, he managed to preach a persuasive speech to the catechumens step by step. Baptism was a simple practice, which could be performed at any time in the fourth century. Of course, since 200 C.E. it used to be performed during the paschal celebration. That is why Gregory was trying to get the catechumens baptized as soon as possible. Baptism involved water, prayer, and the baptismist. There were

primarily young people among the catechumens, and they stayed catechumens for an extended period of time. The church wasn't satisfied with that, so catechesis limits should be imposed, in order to move on to the baptismal practice sooner and get baptized.

Date Range: 372 CE - 395 CE

Region: Asia Minor

Region tags: Asia Minor

Where Pauline Christ groups were located approx. 50-62 CE

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gal. 3:26-29, A' Corinthians 1:12-17.
- Source 2: Gregory of Nyssa, Προς τους βραδύνοντας εις το βάπτισμα

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://greekdownloads.wordpress.com/2014/08/17/ελληνική-πατρολογία-patrologiae-graecae-pg-j-p-migne-cursus-completus-πλήρης/>
- Source 1 Description: <https://www.newadvent.org/fathers/310240.htm>

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/fathers/310240.htm>
- Source 1 Description: <https://greekdownloads.wordpress.com/2014/08/17/ελληνική-πατρολογία-patrologiae-graecae-pg-j-p-migne-cursus-completus-πλήρης/>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– without Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: Don't know

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Don't know

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Don't know

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– I don't know

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– I don't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: It is considered a small part of the patristic texts of the 4th-5th centuries

Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– I don't know

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– I don't know

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– I don't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

- ↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?
 - No
- ↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?
 - No
- ↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
 - Yes
- ↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?
 - Yes
- ↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
 - No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– I don't know

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: You can find it in the "Patrologia Graeca"

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– I don't know

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– I don't know

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Christian Text

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– No

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Heaven & Hell

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The Messiah is Jesus Christ, who has already come to earth

↳ Alive, identified

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ Coming on a specified date

– Yes

Notes: He was born according to Christian tradition on 25th December of the 0 year.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ Coming has already passed

– Yes

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– No

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: Life, love and resurrection

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual of baptism was performed outdoors, as well as indoors. Usually, it took place in the so-called baptismal rooms, which you could find at the bishop's house. Baptism was a private ritual, with very few people involved.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Gregory of Nyssa's oration 40, Brown, Peter. *The Making of Late Antiquity*. London: Harvard University press, 1993.

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Reference: Gregory of Nyssa's oration 40, Guy, L.. "“naked” Baptism in the Early Church: The Rhetoric and the Reality". *The Journal of Religious History* 27, no. (2) (2003): pp. 133-142..

Reference: Gregory of Nyssa's oration 40, Ferguson, E.. *Baptism in the Early Church. History, Theology and Liturgy in the First Five Centuries*. Michigan/Cambridge: William B. Gerdman's Publishing Company, 2009.